

Search for Potent Anthelmintics—Part XI

N^1 -*p*-[4-(Phenyl/*p*-Tolyl)-1-Piperazino]Phenyl- N^3 -Alkyl/Aryl Ureas and Thioureas

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Twenty new N^1 -*p*-[4-(phenyl/*p*-tolyl)-1-piperazino] phenyl- N^3 -alkyl/aryl ureas and thioureas have been synthesised by the condensation of 4-phenyl/*p*-tolyl-1-(aminophenyl) piperazine with various alkyl/aryl isocyanates or aryl isothiocyanates in dry benzene. Out of the six compounds screened against *H.nana* infections in mice, one reduced the worm population by 40%.

PIPERAZINE derivatives have long been used for the treatment of diseases such as ascariasis¹, enterobiasis², filariasis^{3,4} and schistosomiasis^{5,6}. Some urea^{7,8} and thiourea derivatives have also displayed notable anthelmintic activity. Furthermore, the two compounds viz. *N*-(benzylidene)-*p*-(4-*o*-tolyl-1-piperazino)aniline and *N*-(2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzylidene)-*p*-(4-*o*-tolyl-1-piperazino) aniline recently reported by Husain¹¹ et al. showed 94% and 87% efficacy respectively against *H. nana* in mice at an oral dose of 500 mg/kg. Hence, the synthesis and anthelmintic screening of title ureas and thioureas were undertaken.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

Arylisothiocyanates: These were prepared according to the method of Vogel¹².

4-Phenyl/*p*-tolyl-1-(*p*-aminophenyl) piperazines(II):

These were obtained by the reduction of 4-phenyl/*p*-tolyl-1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)piperazine¹¹(I) with Raney nickel and hydrazine hydrate, according to the procedure reported by us earlier¹¹.

Ar = Phenyl or *p*-tolyl.

X = O or S.

R = Alkyl or aryl.

N^1 -*p*-4-(Phenyl/*p*-tolyl)-1-piperazinophenyl- N^3 -alkyl/aryl ureas and thioureas(III):

0.004 Mole of 4-phenyl/*p*-tolyl-1-(*p*-aminophenyl) piperazine(II) was dissolved in 15 ml of dry benzene and to the resulting solution was added 0.004 mole of alkyl/aryl isocyanate or aryl isothiocyanate. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1.5 to 2 hours. The solid obtained on concentration and cooling the reaction mixture was filtered, washed with a little petroleum ether and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether. The yields were in the range of 60 to 70%. The ureas and thioureas thus synthesised are recorded in Table 1.

The compounds numbered 8,10,19 and 20 (Table 1) showed I.R. spectral bands at 3260-3300 cm^{-1} (NH str.), 1625-1640 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 2800 cm^{-1} (C-H str.). Also, the compounds numbered 1,5,11 and 13 showed bands at 3100-3300 cm^{-1} (N-H str.), 1190-1200 cm^{-1} (C=S) and 2800 cm^{-1} (C-H str.).

Bioassay:

Six compounds numbered 5, 7, 10, 11, 16 and 18 (Table 1) were screened by adopting the method of Steward¹³. Thus, the compounds were given orally at a dose of 500 mg/kg to five animals of experimental group. All the compounds except number 18, which reduced the worm population by 40%, were however found to be inactive.

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TABLE 1—N¹-p-[4-(Phenyl/p-tolyl)-1-piperazino] phenyl-N²-alkyl/aryl ureas and thioureas(III)

Sl. No.	X	R	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
<i>Ar = Phenyl</i>						
1.	S	Phenyl	223	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	14.41	14.43
2.	S	p-Tolyl	218	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ S	13.86	13.93
3.	S	o-Methoxyphenyl	217	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS	13.22	13.40
4.	S	p-Methoxyphenyl	215	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ OS	13.18	13.40
5.*	S	m-Chlorophenyl	223	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ SCI	13.57	13.25
6.	S	p-Chlorophenyl	203	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ SCI	13.58	13.25
7.*	S	p-Bromophenyl	202	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ SBr	11.73	11.99
8.	O	n-Propyl	249	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	16.32	16.57
9.	O	n-Butyl	243	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	15.78	15.91
10.*	O	Phenyl	301	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	15.47	15.05
<i>Ar = p-Tolyl</i>						
11.*	S	Phenyl	266	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	13.56	13.93
12.	S	p-Tolyl	233	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ S	13.38	13.46
13.	S	o-Methoxyphenyl	235	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS	12.81	12.96
14.	S	p-Methoxyphenyl	229	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS	12.78	12.96
15.	S	m-Chlorophenyl	219	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ SCI	12.64	12.83
16.*	S	p-Chlorophenyl	221	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ SCI	12.49	12.83
17.	S	p-Bromophenyl	223	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ SBr	11.63	11.69
18.*	O	n-Propyl	259	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	15.73	15.91
19.	O	n-Butyl	257	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	15.72	15.90
20.	O	Phenyl	299	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	14.94	14.57

* Screened for anthelmintic activity.

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